

THE INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY'S ROLE ON TEACHING YOUNG GENERATION

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Annotation: This article focuses on how to conduct lessons with innovative and educational technologies. The creation of e-learning curriculums will further enhance the availability of modern information and communication technologies in teaching these subjects. This, in turn, serves as a major factor for the students to master their knowledge of these subjects and increase the quality and effectiveness of their education.

Key words: innovative technologies, multimedia tools, e-learning, audio, video, graphic, animation, electronic learning resources, computer software, communication.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена тому, как проводить уроки с использованием инновационных и образовательных технологий. Создание учебных программ электронного обучения будет способствовать дальнейшему повышению доступности современных информационных и коммуникационных технологий при преподавании этих предметов. Это, в свою очередь, служит основным фактором, позволяющим студентам овладеть знаниями по этим предметам и повысить качество и эффективность своего обучения.

Ключевые слова: инновационные технологии, мультимедийные средства, электронное обучение, аудио, видео, графика, анимация, электронные учебные ресурсы, компьютерные программы, коммуникация.

In our digital life, all of the actions connected with innovative technologies. The innovative ideas are having considerable impact on our lives day by day. It is time to say without fear that this century is “Modern Technology” century. In fact, all of daily working procedures are associated with new technologies. For instance,

nowadays innovative tools assist us to open miraculous crime by pressing one button of the advanced computer.. All those examples indicates us that if we want to educate young generations we should not avoid utilizing modern technologies. Instead of getting rid of innovation technologies we must figure out how to do it reasonably, what kind of innovative technologies we should choose, when and how much time language learners spend in front of the screen. We should innovate our classroom, which means we need to utilize new technologies such as: interactive board, computers and TVs which are programmed for learners.

Some of those are tool we can definitely introduce in a classroom. Teaching students on multimedia tools is a matter of the present day. The concept of multimedia came into our lives in the early 1990's. First of all what does it mean? Many experts analyze this term differently.

In our opinion, multimedia is a combination of audio, video, graphics and animation effects on the basis of the software and technical means of this informatics. In developed countries, the teaching methodology is currently being implemented in the areas of education. Practice shows that using multimedia tools while learning can be twice as productive. On learning multimedia tools can save time, and the knowledge gained

will stay in memory for a long time as well.

Teaching students on multimedia tools has the following advantages:

- a) the possibility of deeper and more perfecting of the materials;
- b) the desire to communicate closely with new areas of education:
- c) the ability to save time, as a result of reduced educational hours;
- d) The information received is stored long enough in the person's memory and, if necessary, can be used in practice.

Although the idea of using computers in the education system has long since emerged, the use of information technology in all aspects of the education system has been fully implemented since the computers equipped with multimedia devices started. Application of multimedia tools in education will allow:

- providing humanization of education;

- improving the efficiency of the teaching process;
- developing personal qualities of the learner (learning, self-education, self-discipline, self-esteem, creative abilities, interest in learning, attitude to work);
- developing communicative and social skills of the learner;
- The possibility of individualization and differentiation of open and distance education is greatly enhanced by means of individual education of each person using computer and information electronic learning resources;
 - to treat the learner as an active subject, to recognize his/her dignity;
 - taking into account the personal experience and personal characteristics of the learner;
 - Independent learning activities in which the student learns and develops independently;
 - Developing skills in the use of modern teaching technologies that help students adapt to current rapidly changing social conditions to succeed in their professional activities;

While using technologies is an essential part of effective lesson and an important part of classroom management, it should not be assumed that full class would be organized in this manner. Otherwise, lesson may fail because of the lack of attention to students that teachers should pay.

In fact, a teacher should also play a major role controlling the classroom. Multimedia tools are an effective and promising tool for educating a teacher, providing a broader range of data than traditional sources of information, and visual and harmonized, graphs, schemes, but also audio, animations, videos, and more; as well as selecting information consistently in accordance with the level of acceptance and the logic of learners. Actually we can say that multimedia tools will help to increase the motivation of young learners on teaching process as well.

The list of used literature:

1. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/47138>
2. <https://education.cu-portland.edu/blog/classroom-resources/7-reasons-to-use-technology-in-education-lesson-plans/>